

CORRELATION STUDIES ON SEED GERMINATION OF KHIRNI UNDER SHADE NET HOUSE CONDITION

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Abstract

An investigation was carried out on correlation studies on seed germination of Khirni (*Manilkara hexandra*, L.) seedlings under shade net house condition at Department of Horticulture, Vasant Rao Naik Marathwada Agricultural University, Parbhani (M.S.), India during the year 2006-07 and 2007-08. Under shade net house condition, a strong positive correlation of shoot length, number of leaves, fresh weight, dry weight and root length of seedling was exhibited with the germination percentage. Number of days taken to initiate germination was found non-significant with germination percentage of Khirni seeds.

Keywords: Correlation, seed germination, Khirni, Shade net

Introduction

Sapota is one of the most important tropical fruits belonging to the family sapotaceae. India is a leading producer of sapota and area under sapota is estimated to be 107.16 thousand ha with a production of 1284.60 thousand MT and productivity of 11.99 MT/ ha (Anon., 2022). It is a native of South Mexico and Central America. Major sapota producing States are Karnataka, Maharashtra, Gujarat and to some extent in Andhra Pradesh, West Bengal, Orissa and Tamil Nadu. sapota is valued for its sweet and delicious fruits.

The most common commercial method of propagation of sapota at present is inarching and softwood grafting commonly known as "Khirni" or "Rayan" which is considered as a best rootstock for Sapota in India. The germination of Rayan seeds is very poor and growth of seedling is also dead slow and to attain graftable size, it requires about 2-3 years. With this view point, the present study was undertaken at Marathwada Agricultural University, Parbhani, India to study the correlation of seed germination of Khirni under shade net house condition with germination percentage.

Materials and Methods

Germination studies on Khirni seeds were carried out under shade net house condition during April 2006 and subsequently the trial was repeated in April 2007. The experiment was conducted in Completely Randomized Block Design (C.R.D.) with three replications.

The various treatments were T₀-Control (No soaking), T₁- water soaking, T₂-GA₃ 150 ppm, T₃-GA₃ 200 ppm; T₄-Thiourea 1.0%, T₅-Thiourea 1.5%, T₆- Vermiwash 100%, T₇- Coconut water 100%, T₈- Cow dung slurry, T₉ - Cow urine 50%, T₁₀ - Cow urine 100%. For shade net house experiment, the polythene bags of 6 x 9 inches were filled with 2 parts of soil + 1 part of fine sand and + 1 part of FYM. The selected seeds were soaked in above treatments for 24 hours in separate beakers as per the treatment. After that sowing of seeds were carried out in the already filled polythene bags. Observations with regard to germination percentage, number of days taken to initiate germination, shoot length, root length, number of leaves, fresh and dry weight of seedling were recorded. Simple correlation studies were carried out under shade net house condition to find out relationship of germination percentage with shoot length, number of leaves, fresh weight, dry weight and root length of seedling. The correlation (r

value) were computed as per the method suggested by Panse and Sukhatme (1985).

Results and Discussion**Correlation studies of seed germination:**

The character correlation (Table 1 and 2) studied during two consequent years indicated that the seed germination of Khirni correlated with shoot length of seedling, number of leaves per seedling, fresh weight of seedling, dry weight, and root length of seedling under shade net house condition.

During 2006-07 and 2007-08, under net house condition strong positive correlation of shoot length of seedling ($r = 0.923$ and 0.926), number of leaves per seedling ($r = 0.844$ and 0.822), fresh weight of seedling ($r = 0.680$ and 0.715), dry weight of seedling ($r = 0.742$ and 0.763) and root length of seedling ($r = 0.883$ and 0.891) was exhibited with the germination percentage. Number of days taken to initiate germination found was non-significant with germination percentage of Khirni seeds.

These findings are in conformity with the findings of Wagh *et al.* (1998) in Aonla and Reddy and Khan (2001) in Khirni.

Conclusion

Under shade net house condition, a strong positive correlation of shoot length, number of leaves, fresh weight, dry weight and root length of seedling was exhibited with the germination percentage. Number of days taken to initiate germination was found non significant with germination percentage of Khirni seeds.

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Table 1. Correlation studies of germination under shade net house condition with germination percentage during 2006-07

Parameters	No. of Days taken to initiate germination	Shoot length of seedling	No. of leaves per seedling	Fresh weight of seedling	Dry weight of seedling	Root length of seedling	Germination percentage
No. of days taken to initiate germination	1.000	-0.564	-0.380	-0.185	-0.272	-0.525	-0.749
Shoot length of seedling		1.000	0.958	0.852	0.895	0.979	0.923*
No. of leaves per seedling			1.000	0.931	0.9353	0.939	0.844*
Fresh weight of seedling				1.000	0.968	0.845	0.680*
Dry weight of seedling					1.000	0.857	0.752*
Root length of seedling						1.000	0.883*
Germination percentage							1.000

* Significant at 5% level

Table 2. Correlation studies of germination under shade net house condition with germination percentage during 2007-08

Parameters	No. of Days taken to initiate germination	Shoot length of seedling	No. of leaves per seedling	Fresh weight of seedling	Dry weight of seedling	Root length of seedling	Germination percentage
No. of days taken to initiate germination	1.000	-0.370	-0.180	-0.098	-0.160	-0.341	-0.601
Shoot length of seedling		1.000	0.926	0.839	0.871	0.971	0.926*
No. of leaves per seedling			1.000	0.961	0.961	0.899	0.822*
Fresh weight of seedling				1.000	0.962	0.813	0.715*
Dry weight of seedling					1.000	0.819	0.763*
Root length of seedling						1.000	0.891*
Germination percentage							1.000

* Significant at 5% level